

An Evaluation of Library Operations and Services in Academic Libraries in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the operations and services of academic libraries in Anambra State, using the Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) standards as a benchmark. The evaluation focused on key areas such as staffing, ICT usage, and administration in academic libraries to determine compliance with the LRCN standard.

Methodology: A questionnaire was employed as the primary instrument for data collection. The study involved 26 academic librarians from the Prof. Festus Aghagbo Nwako Library, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State. The collected data were analyzed to assess compliance and identify challenges encountered by the libraries.

Hypothesis: The hypothesis posited that academic libraries in Anambra State comply with the LRCN standards in staffing, ICT, and administration but face challenges that hinder full compliance.

Findings/Results: The study revealed that academic libraries in Anambra State generally comply with LRCN standards in the areas of staffing, ICT, and administration. However, the libraries face significant challenges, including poor funding, ignorance, lack of synergy between the National Universities Commission (NUC) and LRCN, and the absence of internal quality assurance mechanisms.

Conclusion: The study concluded that while academic libraries in Anambra State show compliance with LRCN standards, operational challenges undermine their ability to fully meet the requirements. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving library operations and services.

Recommendations: The study recommends that university authorities prioritize employing the right categories of staff in sufficient numbers to meet LRCN's required staff-to-student and staff-to-collection ratios. University librarians should develop and implement effective ICT

policies to ensure a coordinated and resourceful ICT environment, enabling active participation in today's ICT-driven global landscape.

Keywords: Library Services, Academic libraries, Librarian's Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN), Nigeria.

Introduction

A university library is a type of academic library, established by tertiary institutions to support teaching, learning, and research. These libraries are created to provide information resources for the education of both middle- and high-level skilled manpower, contributing to society's advancement. The role of the university library in the university system has led scholars to variously refer to it as the brain and the center of intellectual activities (Eyiolorunshe & Eluwole, 2017). According to Chukwunji and Umeji (2020), it is the heart, center of excellence and lifeblood of the university system. Additionally, it can be described as the rallying point of academic and research activities within the university. In fulfilling its role, the university library collects, organizes, processes, preserves, stores, and disseminates human knowledge recorded in various formats, such as print (books, journals, etc.), non-print (audio, audiovisual, microfilm, etc.), and electronic resources (ICT-enhanced materials/digital objects – e-journals, DVDs, CD-ROMs, etc.). Moreover, for quality service delivery and efficient operations, the necessary resources must be provided to maintain the library's standard.

However, quality assurance is essential for effective and efficient library services, hence the need for standards. This necessity led the Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) to issue a draft called the *Minimum Standards and Guidelines (MS&G)* for academic libraries in Nigeria, which covers infrastructure, document management processes, ICT, administration, governance, staffing, among others (LRCN, 2014). Specifically, this study is focused on three aspects of the *Minimum Standards and Guidelines (MS&G)*: staffing, ICT, and administration. The importance of staffing in any organization, including university libraries, cannot be overstated.

The *Minimum Standards and Guidelines* for staffing ensure that the university library has the right caliber of staff required to effectively achieve its objectives. Staffing is the lifeblood of any organization, as it is the human element that drives the organization towards fulfilling its goals and objectives. This aligns with the position of Issa, Idowu, Amusan, Ojokuku, Adedeji, and Oguntayo (2016), who stated that the objectives of establishing an organization would amount to nothing without human resources. Therefore, it is only with the right combination of staff that a university library will be able to fulfill its mandate (Issa et al., 2016). Anything short of this leads to poor service delivery.

On the other hand, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), since its adoption in library services, has proven to be an essential tool for effective and efficient service delivery. ICT is required in all library operations, from selection and acquisition to processing, preserving, accessing, and disseminating library resources. ICT provides speed, massive storage capacity, and access to a vast array of current information resources from around the world, which is exactly what university libraries need to meet their ever-evolving and increasing users' demands (Uzoagba & Okiche, 2018).

Administration is also crucial to the growth and development of an academic library. Arua and Udoh (2019) indicates that the concept of "administration" is one that lacks a single, clear definition, as it can be seen as an executive function directed towards getting the job done. This view is shared by Aderibigbe and Olla (2014), who agree that administration can be seen as a governmental action concerned with the executive part of government, dealing with the formulation and enforcement of policies.

Herbert, Thompson, and Smithburg, as cited in Zaharia (2011) describe administration as the activities of the executive branch of national, state, and local governments. According to Zaharia (2011), administration is a set of authorities working together and operating as a coherent system that, through its activities, aims to satisfy organizational interests continuously and in accordance with social expectations. Nkuna and Sebola (2015) argue that the practice of administration cannot be separated from the capabilities of people in leadership positions within any organization.

Furthermore, Umeozorm and Emasealu (2016) posited that the administration of a university library is very important. The university library is a key component of the university system; thus, its head is a principal officer of the university and a member of the university senate, management team, and other high-level committees. According to these authors, this makes it mandatory for the head of the university library (referred to as the University Librarian in Nigeria) to be a high-ranking professional librarian, often with the rank of Professor. This status enables them to participate actively in various roles and assignments, and they should conduct evaluation exercises periodically to ensure efficient and effective library service delivery.

According to Adebayo (2019), the evaluation of library operations and services in universities enhances and guarantees value, as it provides indicators for assessing individual libraries based on given parameters. Regular assessments are necessary for continuous improvement. While the National Universities Commission (NUC) conducts accreditation exercises to ensure quality, it does not appear to have a detailed benchmark for university libraries comparable to that of the Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN). The NUC's benchmarks are embedded in the Self Study Form of academic departments and consist of open-ended

questions rather than set criteria. For example, there is no specific provision for staffing in these study guides.

To ensure compliance with the set minimum standards and guidelines, provisions must be made for monitoring and evaluation, both by individual libraries and universities, to confirm that the right staff, resources, and services are in place. External bodies, such as the NUC, conduct accreditation exercises in universities to ensure compliance with minimum academic standards and other requirements. For university libraries to meet the LRCN Minimum Standards and Guidelines, and to satisfy stakeholders, an internal monitoring and evaluation mechanism, from both the university and the library itself, must be properly implemented. Therefore, based on this background, this study conducted research on the evaluation of library operations and services in academic libraries in Anambra State using the LRCN standards.

Statement of the Problem

Academic libraries are the focal point of all research and academic activities in universities. They collect, process, preserve, and disseminate various information and materials in all formats relevant to the institution's courses of study. To ensure this, the Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN), in 2014, produced a document prescribing the expected standards and minimum guidelines for academic libraries, including staffing, ICT, and administration/governance, for effective and efficient service delivery.

Regrettably, however, none of the accreditation exercises include librarians as members of the teams. The LRCN does not conduct monitoring and evaluation through accreditation or certification of academic libraries; instead, they certify and register practitioners and delegate the responsibility of monitoring to the officers in charge of the academic libraries. However, this approach is flawed, as it essentially results in university librarians evaluating themselves. This situation has contributed to the poor state of libraries.

Hence, the poor state of libraries and their services would result in poor usage, which may also lead to poor student academic performance and inadequate information literacy skills for lifelong learning. The consequence is that the university library fails to meet its objectives. Therefore, this study sought to assess the evaluation of library operations and services in academic libraries in Anambra State using the LRCN standards. The following research questions guided the study:

Research Questions

- RQ1. Are academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN on Staffing?
- RQ2. Are academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN on ICT?
- RQ3. Are academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN on Administration?
- RQ4. What are the challenges encountered by the library in complying with LRCN standard in library evaluation?

Literature Review

Some services rendered in Academic libraries

According to Fabunmi (2012), Academic libraries are operationally defined as organized collections of information resources (print and non-print) which form an integral part of tertiary institution. In essence, the academic libraries provide resources to support the teaching and research activities of their parent institutions.

The objectives of academic libraries according to Ifidon (2009) are: (a) Provision of information resources for undergraduate instruction, term papers and project as well as for supplementary reading. (b) Provision of information resources in support of faculty, external and collaborated researches. (c) Provision of information resources in support of post-graduate research. (d) Provision of expensive standard work especially in the professional disciplines. (e) Provision of information resources for personal self-development. (f) Provision of specialized information on the region within which the university is situated.

Compliance of LRCN on Staffing by Academic Libraries in Anambra State

To facilitate academic success, academic libraries must provide access to a broad range of information resources. Reference and referral services, orientation activities, and instruction sessions that teach students the critical thinking skills necessary for using library information resources are one of the basic services provided by the staff particularly to new students of the institutions in Nigeria. Varied and innovative orientation programmes to new users of the library include teaching by personal contact and through the preparation and use of instructional information resources in various formats. Introducing the library users to the library activities, provide a gateway to all future inquiries, not only preparing the users as independent users but also teaching them to use information sources as citizens, as consumers, as professionals, and for recreational purposes.

LRCN Minimum Standards Library on ICT

According to Sali and Abubakar (2012), library services in the 21st century are mostly done with the aid of Information and Communication Technology. Information and Communication Technology has impacted and improved all sectors of the economy and the library is not left out of this. The growth of ICT has led to increase demand for information and it is changing the way to which information is handled. With ICT in libraries, librarians are faced with a great task of incorporating ICT to the services they render.

ICT has aided a fast delivery of library services as such clientele need not to spend much time within the library before their needs are met. Furthermore, ICT has revolutionized library services in the 21st century (Ekeyong, 2017). ICT has been widely discussed in all spheres of life, including the library. The importance of ICT to library development is crucial. ICT help libraries provide e-resources to augment its physical materials holding (Adebayo, 2019).

This corroborate the position of Uzoagba and Okiche (2018) that libraries use online search to search for useful websites and articles because it is not possible for any one library to acquire all needed materials, hence, most Nigerian libraries rely on online resources to complement their collection. This underscores the importance of ICT in academic library, hence the need for implementable ICT policies both by the institution and the library. However, Adebayo, (2019) noted that the current ICT infrastructure in Nigeria cannot enable Nigerians or Nigerian universities to participate fully in the global information society. Hence, the narrative seems to have been changing, though gradually. This is evident in some studies, for example, Chukwuji and Umeji (2019) discovered that there is high availability of ICT facilities/components in Kashim Ibrahim Library (KIL), Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. The study by Madumere, Uwakwe and Mbajiorgu (2015) reported high availability of ICT-based facilities in University of Nigeria library. The findings have shown that Nigerian university libraries are embracing ICT, though slowly, perhaps due to paucity of fund.

Ugwu and Ekere (2014) studied the Status of ICT enabled library and information services in University of Nigeria, Nsukka library system. The purpose of the study is to know the level of compliance with LRCN standards regarding ICT provision in the library. Questionnaire was used to collect data from all the professional staff in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka library. The study found ICT facilities are inadequate in the library and that the available facilities are not functioning. The study concluded that poor funding is one of the problems of ICT development in university library.

Compliance of LRCN on Administration

LRCN was established by Act of 1995 with the mandate to develop libraries in Nigeria through regulatory policies, guidelines and standards. In pursuance to this mandate, the Council developed Draft Minimum Standards and Guidelines for academic library (LRCN, 2014) and available at www.lrcn.ng.gov.

Administration is a must in any organization, including the university library. No matter how well established in terms of equipment and facilities without human resource of different categories in quantity and quality, that organization may never achieve its goals. No wonder, Shehu (2012) states that LRCN has given a clear and unequivocal definition of different administrative categories in librarianship and the level of training appropriate for each of the categories. This level of training has helped academic libraries designate duties to administrative heads appropriately. In another study at the Federal University of Technology Minna Library, Men and Israel (2017) revealed that 19 (29%) of the respondents are professional staff, 18 (28%) are para-professional while 28 (43%) of the respondents are non-professional staff.

The result therefore showed that the library has higher number of non-professional staff. Issa, et al. (2016) studied administrative implications of the four university libraries in Ilorin, Kwara State. The purpose of the study is to know the level of compliance with LRCN standards regarding administration of university libraries in Nigeria. Questionnaire was used to collect data from librarians in the four university libraries in Ilorin, Kwara State. The study found that with the exception of Landmark University Library the other three, University of Ilorin Library, Al-Hakim Library and Kwara State University Library, have inadequate administration and staff in relation to their total collection, as well as in relation to their user population. Furthermore, Al-Hakim, Kwara State University Library also has challenges of inadequate mix and number of staff. University of Ilorin Library has a bottom-heavy administrative situation with shortage of both middle and upper levels of both academic and paraprofessionals.

The Challenges of Academic Library Operations and Services in Nigeria.

a. Incompetence: Some university librarians at the Nigerian University are not able to meet the challenges, especially in the provision of information services. They do not want technology and take the application of computers to make the library a real outlet. For this reason, they are reluctant to use new technologies. Tanawade (2011) states that many librarians lack self-reliance in the face of growing information technology. This slows the delivery of the service and delays productivity. Hayati & Jowkar (2008) believe that the most problematic factors that slow down the process of computer introduction, based on the lack of knowledge of librarians and users with computers and database search.

b. Lack of knowledge of technology: Okonkwo and Anaehobi (2021) added that many librarians lack confidence in the face of increasing information technology and this slows service delivery and retard productivity. In addition, most problematic factors which slows down the adoption of information technologies stem from unfamiliarity of academic librarians and users with computers and searching databases, lack of technology literacy. It can include technological efficiency such as the ability to communicate responsibly with appropriate technology, problem solving, and access, manage, integrate, evaluate training, and create the lack of basic skills in the use of information technology has become a bottleneck for better library services. Anyira (2011) adds that librarians who do not have advanced ICT skills cannot provide effective information to improve learning. Learning is needed in all disciplines for the purpose of lifetime to acquire knowledge and skills in the 21st century. In other words, that the biggest challenge facing the academic library is not spending a lot of money, but lack of librarians' competence and information library services, so lack of skills among librarians is a major impediment to providing services to the library in digital age.

c. Low Internet Connection: The Internet plays a major role in digital information, but equal access to the Internet has not yet been achieved in Nigerian university libraries. Current Internet connections to most people are slow. Olabude (2007) notes that many constraints have led to poor Internet development in Africa, one of which is the initial investment for the installation of Internet equipment. This is because almost all African countries have large debts and are lacking currencies to buy assets. Chigbu and Dim (2012) argue that there are no efficient and energy-efficient connections that can serve as a starting point for the development of Internet services in Africa. When these services are available, the nature of expensive services is another important factor. Professionals in developing countries are challenged due to low skills in ICT.

d. Insufficient energy supply: Nigerian energy is in a desperate state. There is no ongoing failure that prevents the effective implementation of information services. Most libraries use alternative energy sources such as power generators to function. However, these machines are prone to maintenance problems, high costs of diesel and gasoline. The resulting effect was the provision of epilepsy services.

f. Low funding: Money is the tool that connects the university library to provide effective information services. Money is needed to obtain ICT equipment, Internet subscriptions, staff training, reimbursement and maintenance. The strength of the library lies in its information resources, printed and online. Funds are needed to manage a range of services in the university library, but government support in the education sector is inadequate. Umeozor and Emasealu, (2016) added that problems with computer applications in African libraries include indifference and inadequate government funding. Funding is essential for excellent library services.

g. Copyright: It is very easy to copy, duplicate, transmit and distribute digital information. Copyright has been violated in a digital environment because it has no control over access to content and reproduction of multiple copies of digital media.

Methodology

The research design for this study is a case study design. According to Nworgu (2015), a case study is an intensive investigation aimed at thoroughly understanding a specific social unit. The social unit may be an individual, a group of individuals, or an institution. Therefore, this study is designed to evaluate library operations and services in academic libraries in Anambra State using the LRCN standards.

The population of the study consists of 26 academic librarians from the Prof. Festus Aghagbo Nwako Library at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State. Since the population is small and manageable, no sampling was necessary. The entire population of 26 academic librarians will be used in the study.

The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers, titled "Evaluation of Library Operations and Services in Academic Libraries (ELOSAL)" Questionnaire. It was designed to assess compliance with the LRCN standards on staffing, ICT, and administration in academic libraries in Anambra State.

Data collected in the study were analyzed using weighted mean scores to answer the research questions. A cutoff point of 2.5 was used. Any item with a weighted mean above 2.5 was considered as being agreed upon by the respondents, while any mean score below 2.5 was regarded as being disagreed upon by the respondents.

The respondents were required to respond to each of the items on a four-point rating Likert scale ranging from;

- SA = Strongly Agree = 4
- A = Agree = 3
- SD= Strongly Disagree = 2
- D = Disagree =1.

The students were requested to respond to the statements by choosing the most appropriate response from the Likert Scale. Therefore, the weighted mean will be worked out with the following formula:

$$X = \frac{\text{Sum total}}{\text{Number}} X = \frac{4 + 3 + 2 + 1}{4} \text{weighted mean } (x) = \frac{10}{4} = 2$$

Results

Table 1: Mean Scores of academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN on Staffing

S/N	Items	X	Remarks
1.	Professional librarians in my institution has first degree in LIS	3.30	Agreed
2.	Professional staff in my institution have ICT competencies and literacy skills	3.40	Agreed
3.	Professional staff in my institution have evidence of publications in scholarly works	3.08	Agreed
4.	Professional librarians in my institution are registered with the (LRCN)	2.86	Agreed

Based on the result of table 1 above, it shows that academic libraries in Anambra State are complying with the LRCN standard on Staffing.

Table 2: Mean scores for academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN on ICT

S/N	Items	X	Remarks
5	Library has space for installation of computers for users	3.53	Agreed
6	There is adequate ICT personnel for computer maintenance	3.25	Agreed
7	There are ICT hardware and software provided to adequately facilitate the information management needs of the library	3.50	Agreed
8	Information resources are digitized	3.75	Agreed
9	There are established ICT policies to guide adoption and maintenance of ICT Gadgets	3.45	Agreed

Based on the result of table 2 above, it shows that academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN standard on ICT.

Table 3: Mean scores for academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN standard on Administration

S/N	Items	X	Remarks
10.	Librarians have the desirable managerial administrative skills and experience	3.92	Agreed
11.	Interact with faculty members on curricular and instructional matters and research activities	3.75	Agreed
12.	The vision and mission of the library is in line with the wider vision and mission of the parent institution	3.75	Agreed
13.	There is a library organogram indicating hierarchy and relationship of the component parts of the library	3.89	Agreed
14.	Plans for continuous development and improvement of library resources and services	3.44	Agreed

Based on the result of table 3 above, it shows that academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN standard on administration.

Table 4: Mean scores for the challenges encountered by the library in complying with LRCN standard in library evaluation

S/N	Items	X	Remarks
15	Poor funding	3.53	Agreed
16	Ignorant of some academic librarians of the existence and provisions of the LRCN standards and guidelines	3.25	Agreed
17	Lack of synergy between NUC and LRCN	3.50	Agreed
18	NUC's non coverage of all the LRCN requirements	3.75	Agreed
19	Lack of internal quality assurance mechanism in the academic libraries	3.45	Agreed

Based on the result of table 4 above, it shows that poor funding, ignorance, lack of synergy between NUC and LRCN and lack of internal quality assurance in the academic libraries are the challenges encountered by libraries in complying with LRCN standard in library evaluation.

Table 5: Mean scores on the proffered solutions to the challenges encountered by the library in complying with LRCN standard

S/N	Items	X	Remarks
20.	Heavy funding of the academic libraries	3.92	Agreed
21.	Creating awareness to academic libraries of the existence and provisions of the LRCN standards and guidelines	3.75	Agreed
22.	Improved synergy between NUC and LRCN	3.75	Agreed
23.	NUC's coverage of all the LRCN requirements	3.89	Agreed
24.	Improved internal quality assurance mechanism in the academic libraries	3.44	Agreed

Based on the result of table 5 above, it shows that heavy funding of the academic libraries, creating awareness on existence of LRCN standard guidelines, NUC's coverage of all LRCN requirements and improved internal mechanism are the proffered solutions to the challenges encountered by the library in complying with LRCN standard.

Discussion of findings

Academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN standard on Staffing

Based on the findings of table 1, it was discovered that Academic libraries in Anambra State are complying with the LRCN on Staffing. This is in line with the position of Issa, Idowu, Amusan, Ojokuku, Adedeji, and Oguntayo, (2016) that the objectives of setting up an organization will amount to nothing without human resources. Therefore, it follows that it is only with the right combination of staff that the university library will be able to deliver on its mandates (Ojokuku, Adedeji, & Oguntayo, 2016).

Academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN standard on ICT

Based on the findings of table 2, it was discovered that Academic libraries in Anambra State are complying with the LRCN standard on ICT This findings is in line with Nkamnebe, Udem and Nkamnebe, 2014) who asserts that ICT are right descriptions, hence, it can also be said to be the rallying point of academic and research activities in the university. In furtherance of its role, university library collects, organize/process, preserve/store and disseminate human knowledge recorded in various information-carrying formats, like prints (books, journals etc),

non-prints (audio, audio visual, microfilm among others) and e-resources (ICT enhanced materials /digital objects – e-journals, DVD or CD-ROM and many more).

This corroborate the position of Uzoagba and Okiche (2018) that libraries use online search to search for useful websites and articles because it is not possible for any one library to acquire all needed materials, hence, most Nigerian libraries rely on online resources to complement their collection. This underscores the importance of ICT in academic library, hence the need for implementable ICT policies both by the institution and the library.

Academic libraries in Anambra State complying with the LRCN standard on Administration

Based on the findings of table 3, it was discovered that Academic libraries in Anambra State are complying with the LRCN standard on administration. This finding is in line with Umeozor and Emasealu (2016) that university librarians participated actively in managing their libraries as well as on issues concerning their universities. This is in consonance with the LRCN on administration /governance of universities libraries. Leadership was the most important.

The challenges encountered by the library in complying with LRCN standard in library evaluation

Based on the findings of table 4, it was discovered that poor funding, ignorance, lack of synergy between NUC and LRCN and lack of internal quality assurance in the academic libraries are the challenges encountered by libraries in complying with LRCN standard in library evaluation in Anambra State. This finding is in line with the finding of Ekere, Ugwu and Ekere (2014) that poor funding is one of the problems of development in university library.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that academic libraries in Anambra State are complying with the LRCN standards on staffing, ICT, and administration. However, challenges such as poor funding, lack of awareness, insufficient synergy between the NUC and LRCN, and the absence of internal quality assurance in academic libraries hinder full compliance with the LRCN standards in library evaluation in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are based on the findings of this study:

1. University libraries should strive to maintain the appropriate categories of staff, both in quality and quantity, to meet the required staff-to-student and staff-to-collection ratios

as outlined by the LRCN. This will enable them to provide effective and efficient services and achieve their objectives.

2. The study also recommends increased funding for academic libraries, raising awareness about the existence of the LRCN standard guidelines, ensuring that the NUC covers all LRCN requirements, and improving internal mechanisms to address the challenges faced by libraries in complying with LRCN standards in Anambra State

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